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Extension of catalyst lifetime for application of diesel-fueled pre-reforming in a commercial SOFC system

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Abstract

While pre-reforming of natural gas with nickel catalysts is an industrially established process, pre-reforming of higher hydrocarbons like diesel is more challenging, as the nickel catalysts used in the process show rapid catalyst deactivation. The reasons for this are sulfur poisoning, coke deposition and sintering [1]. Coke formation can be minimized by keeping a certain steam-to-carbon ratio and by running the process at a temperature which is high enough to prevent polymeric gum formation and below temperatures where whisker carbon can be formed. Christensen et al. [2] present suitable values for these parameters, but heat integration and recirculation of mass flows in a SOFC system make temperature control in the adiabatic pre-reformer significantly more complex than in a laboratory reactor. As sulfur poisoning cannot be prevented effectively when commercial diesel is used for process gas generation, a selective adsorber is placed upstream of the pre-reformer to remove sulfur components. Currently running experiments shall validate the assumed catalyst lifetime enhancement when using fully desulfurized diesel.

Non-ideal conditions can lead to an early catalyst failure going along with a slip of higher hydrocarbons through the reactor. As this can cause severe damage at the anode downstream of the reformer, the operator of the system must always know the condition of the catalyst. Therefore, a method for online measurement of the catalyst condition is required. Previous experiments have shown that the temperature profile, which arises in the adiabatic pre-reformer due to endothermic reforming reaction and exothermic methanation and water-gas-shift reaction, is suited for this purpose. One aim of the experiments is to find a method that allows extrapolation of catalyst lifetime at an early stage of deactivation.

So far more than 3000 hours of continuous pre-reforming with complete conversion of higher hydrocarbons have been achieved [3]. The objective of diesel pretreatment and adjustment of reforming parameters is pushing the catalyst lifetime to more than 8000 hours so that the SOFC system can be operated one year without catalyst change.

Introduction

Unlike PEM based fuel cell systems, stationary SOFC systems are typically fueled with natural gas, as the internal reforming of methane at the anode can be used for cooling the fuel cell stack. Furthermore, in contrast to hydrogen there is an existing pipeline network for natural gas. However, for certain mobile applications like shipping or heavy-duty traffic liquid fuels like diesel profit from their significantly higher volumetric energy density as well as easy storage and transportability. Compared to compressed hydrogen at 700 bar the volumetric calorific value of diesel is more than four times higher and compared to liquefied natural gas it is about twice as high [4]. Therefore, SOFC systems using diesel fuel are a promising way for ship owners to reduce pollutant emissions arising from on-board electricity generation. Additionally, the high electric efficiency of up to 60 % leads to a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions of up to 25 % compared to electricity generation with gas turbines or diesel fueled internal combustion engines.

To be used in the fuel cell, diesel as well as natural gas must be converted into a hydrogen rich gas mixture by steam reforming. Natural gas mainly consists of methane, carbon dioxide and small amounts of higher hydrocarbons like ethane and propane, whereas diesel is a mixture of many different compounds like alkanes and aromatics ranging from 9 to 22 carbon atoms per molecule. Therefore, the reforming of diesel tends to form carbonaceous deposits on the catalyst narrowing the values for parameters such as temperature and steam-to-carbon ratio to a small operating window. Another reason for rapid catalyst deactivation is sulfur poisoning, since even small amounts of sulfur which can be found in ultra-low sulfur diesel strongly adsorb on the active sites of nickel catalysts and block them for further reactions [5].

The objective of this work is to prove that catalyst deactivation during diesel pre-reforming can be reduced to an acceptable degree for a commercial application when using fully desulfurized diesel and applying suitable operating parameters.

1. Scientific Approach

Adiabatic pre-reforming of light feedstocks like natural gas or naphtha is an established process used in the chemical industry to convert all higher hydrocarbons in the feed stream and thereby preventing soot formation in the reformer. Unlike steam reforming which is carried out at temperatures above 800 °C, a pre-reformer is typically operated in the range of 400 – 500 °C. This causes a shift in the chemical equilibrium resulting in an incomplete conversion of methane. The remaining share of methane, which is about 10 – 15 % of the dry gas volume, is beneficial for heat integration of an SOFC system. The reason for this is the fact that the endothermic reforming reaction of methane takes place at the anodic part of the fuel cell using excess heat produced during fuel cell operation.

Feasibility of pre-reforming heavier feedstock like diesel has been proven by many authors [5,6]. The endothermic reforming reaction is irreversible for all hydrocarbons except methane. Therefore, the reactions in the process can be summarized as irreversible reforming (1) accompanied by reversible methanation (3) and water-gas-shift (2).

Christensen et al. [2] provide a detailed understanding of catalyst degradation mechanisms as there are mainly coke formation and sulfur poisoning. They describe seven different types of carbonaceous deposits formed during pre-reforming of higher

hydrocarbons mainly depending on steam-to-carbon ratio and temperature level. Due to the heterogenous character of diesel fuel coke formation cannot be completely prevented, yet it can be sufficiently reduced for a long-term process when applying suitable process parameters. The other dominating degradation mechanism when reforming diesel fuel is sulfur poisoning. Sulfur strongly adsorbs on the active sites of nickel catalysts and blocks them for further reactions. Even small concentrations of less than 10 ppm sulfur which can be present in European road diesel according to DIN EN 590 cause rapid catalyst failure. Even though these mechanisms are thoroughly investigated and understood [2], diesel pre-reforming has not been developed to a technology readiness level that would make it suitable for commercial applications. Besides the complex desulfurization of diesel to values below 1 ppm sulfur, reasons for this might be the generally higher costs of diesel compared to natural gas as well as the lack of an application that would profit from using liquid fuels. However, as regulations for pollutant and greenhouse-gas emissions in shipping are becoming stricter, mobile diesel fueled SOFC systems seem to be a promising technology that depends on a stable reforming process.

Figure 1: Experimental setup with gas supply via mass flow controller controllers (MFC) and temperature measurement along the reactor length with thermocouples (TC)

2. Experiments

Experiments for the determination of catalyst lifetime depending on operating parameters and sulfur content were carried out in a tubular reactor with an active volume of about one liter. Given the small size of the reactor an adiabatic operation was not feasible. Therefore, heat losses were partly compensated with an external electrical heating. As the reformer is intended as a part of the SOFC system, a recirculation of anode off-gas was simulated by dosing hydrogen, carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide into the reactor. The respective volume flows for each component were calculated with a system model. Diesel was evaporated on a heated mesh and mixed with water vapor and recirculated gases before

entering the reformer. The experiments were executed at atmospheric pressure. The inlet temperature of the reformer was derived from a system model as well and set between 500 and 600 °C. Temperatures in the reformer are only influenced by external heat losses and the energy needed for the endothermic reforming reaction. Hence, the temperature profile in the reactor provides valuable information about the status of the reaction and the ageing of the catalyst. To visualize the temperature profile in the reformer, eight thermocouples were placed along the flow direction. At the same positions small tubes for gas removal were placed to analyze the gas composition alongside the reactor. Concentrations of carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide and methane were measured with a nondispersive infrared sensor. Hydrogen concentrations were determined via thermal conductivity. At the reformer outlet the product gas was completely condensed and analyzed for traces of higher hydrocarbons. Catalyst failure was defined as the operation time at which significant amounts of higher hydrocarbons could be measured at the reformer outlet. This can be seen in an increase of total organic carbon from about 5 ppm to several hundred ppm and in a thin oil phase on the condensate of the product gas. In several short-term pre-tests the commercial nickel-based catalyst AR-401 by Haldor Topsoe showed the best performance when reforming ultra-low sulfur diesel and was therefore chosen for the long-term experiments. The range of possible values for steam-to-carbon ratio to prevent soot formation was determined via equilibrium calculations and verified by previous experiments. The focus of the investigations for catalyst lifetime enhancement was therefore put on the influence of small amounts of sulfur. In the first experiment a US-diesel according to ASTM D 975 with 15 ppm sulfur was used for continuous pre-reforming till catalyst failure. In the second run those results were compared to a desulfurized diesel with less than 1 ppm sulfur.

3. Results

Figure 2: Change of temperature profile over reactor length during pre-reforming of diesel fuel with 15 ppm sulfur in the first 1200 hours of continuous reforming

Figure 2 shows a typical temperature profile that occurs during diesel pre-reforming. Starting from the temperature in the mixing chamber there is a strong initial temperature drop when entering the catalyst caused by the endothermic reforming reaction. After passing a temperature minimum the exothermic methanation leads to a rise of the reactor temperature to a second maximum. As the overall reaction is endothermic the temperature at the reformer outlet is significantly lower than the inlet temperature.

In the first experiment (Figure 2) diesel with 15 ppm sulfur is used for the reforming process. After 100 hours of reforming the temperature profile in the reactor is characterized by a steep temperature drop till about 1/8 of the reactor length followed by a linear rise till half of the reactor length indicating a high catalyst activity. Yet, when compared to the profile that arises when using diesel with less than 1 ppm sulfur (Figure 3), a major difference can be seen when focusing on the first thermocouple just behind the reactor inlet. While the temperature drops about 50 K between mixing chamber and first thermocouple after 100 hours of reforming with < 1 ppm diesel it sinks only about 10 K after reforming with 15 ppm diesel for the same time. This shows that catalyst activity at the reformer entrance is significantly lowered after only a short time of reforming with 15 ppm diesel. Even after 700 and 1200 hours of process operation only minor changes in the temperature profile of the < 1 ppm experiment can be measured indicating a very slow catalyst degradation. The initial drop between mixing chamber and first thermocouple is still 35 K after 1200 hours of operation. In contrast, the temperature profile of the 15 ppm sulfur experiment changes drastically after 700 and 1200 operation hours.

Between mixing chamber and first thermocouple no temperature-drop and consequently no reaction can be seen after 700 hours of reforming. The temperature minimum moves downstream the reactor to 1/4 of the reactor length after 700 hours and to 3/8 after 1200 hours going along with a general flattening of the profile. Catalyst failure with slip of higher hydrocarbons occurred after 2700 hours in the experiment with 15 ppm sulfur. The experiment with less than 1 ppm sulfur was still running at the time of this publication. As the temperature profile only showed minor changes in the first 1200 hours, methods for extrapolation of catalyst lifetime which are based on the shift of the profile couldn't be applied.

Figure 3: Comparison of changes in temperature profiles over reactor length during pre-reforming of diesel fuel with < 1 ppm sulfur (left side) and 15 ppm sulfur (right side) in the first 1200 hours of continuous reforming

Another possibility to determine catalyst activity is by measuring methane concentrations along the reactor length. As no methane is present in the recirculated gas, all methane is produced by methanation. Figure 4 shows methane concentrations for the first 1000 hours of the 15 ppm sulfur experiment. Concentrations rise till they reach chemical equilibrium and only change slightly from that point as the temperature changes over reactor length cause minor changes in the position of the equilibrium concentrations. After 24 hours of operation methane concentrations reach chemical equilibrium at 1/4 of the reactor length. After 1000 hours the increase is significantly slower due to catalyst degradation and reaches the equilibrium at half of the reactor length. At the end of the reactor all gas concentrations reached chemical equilibrium even after slip of higher hydrocarbons. When comparing these profiles to the experiment with less than 1 ppm sulfur present in the fuel (Figure 5), it becomes evident, that a strong catalyst degradation already takes place in the first 24 hours of the 15 ppm experiment. While equilibrium in the 15 ppm experiment is reached after 1/4 of the reactor length after 24 hours, methane concentrations reach the equilibrium after 1/8 of the reactor length in the <1 ppm experiment. Although catalyst degradation is clearly visible in this experiment, the equilibrium concentration after 1000 hours is still reached at 1/4 of the reactor length.

Figure 4: Change of methane concentrations over reactor length during 1000 hours of pre-reforming with 15 ppm sulfur diesel

Therefore, it can be concluded that catalyst activity after 1000 hours of reforming with diesel with less than 1 ppm sulfur is similar to the activity after only 24 hours when reforming with 15 ppm sulfur diesel.

Figure 5: Comparison of changes of methane concentrations over reactor length during 1000 hours of pre-reforming with < 1 ppm (left side) and 15 ppm sulfur (right side) diesel

4. Conclusion

The experiments showed that even small amounts of sulfur have an enormous influence on catalyst degradation. While the catalyst degraded very quickly with 15 ppm sulfur in the fuel, almost no loss in catalyst activity could be seen with less than 1 ppm sulfur. As expected, the change of the temperature profile in the reactor is an easy and reliable possibility to evaluate catalyst activity. Due to the low catalyst degradation when using diesel with less than 1 ppm sulfur, methods for extrapolating catalyst lifetime could not be applied, as they are based on the movement of characteristic points in the temperature profile along the reactor.

Measuring methane concentrations along the reactor length also provides valuable information about the progress of catalyst degradation, yet it does not seem to be an option for commercial systems. The gas composition at the reformer outlet however, is not suited to evaluate catalyst degradation, as it still reaches chemical equilibrium when higher hydrocarbons slip through the reactor. Although the experiment with less than 1 ppm sulfur wasn't finished at the time of publication, the low catalyst degradation in the first 1200 hours of operation indicates that a catalyst lifetime of 8000 hours, which was defined as sufficient for the intended commercial application, can be reached.

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